

Unraveling Multi-Stage AI Threat Scenarios with MITRE ATLAS: A Probabilistic Risk Analysis Using Absorbing Markov Chains ^{*}

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Abstract. Prompt Injection, ranked LLM01 in the OWASP Top 10 for LLM Applications, is widely regarded as difficult to fully mitigate, and probabilistic evaluation of chained multi-stage attacks remains limited. We formulate a four-step MITRE ATLAS-derived attack scenario as a non-homogeneous absorbing Markov chain and evaluate Meta Llama3:8B on Tensor Trust scripts (776 Hijacking, 230 Extraction). Five incrementally hardened prompt-level defense configurations, which we call Verbose Refusal (VR0–VR4), improved monotonically under both single-stage Hijacking and chained multi-stage evaluation. However, manual analysis of residual failures revealed Refusal-Induced Leakage (RIL): the model refuses, yet discloses protected information within its own explanation. Contrasted with Compliance-Induced Leakage (CIL), we find that while hardening substantially reduces overall leakage, it increases the share of residual leakage taking the RIL form, a pattern confirmed across both refusal paradigms and all hardening levels. Redesigning refusal as Silent Refusal (SR) achieved comparable Extraction defense to VR but caused far more unnecessary refusals on benign prompts, a security–usability trade-off not offset by a security advantage. Adding a three-layer external guardrail, VR4 with the guardrail attained the strongest defense while keeping overblocking low, making VR plus the guardrail the most favorable configuration overall.

Keywords: LLM security · Prompt injection · Absorbing Markov chain · MITRE ATLAS · Refusal-Induced Leakage

1 Introduction

Prompt Injection attacks have been associated with real-world security incidents, including the compromise of Lenovo’s support bot “Lena” via session cookie theft [1] and a Chevrolet dealer chatbot manipulated into recognizing a \$1 vehicle sale as a “legally binding offer” [2]. These incidents illustrate two

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major attack categories against LLM applications: Extraction, which attempts to exfiltrate confidential information, and Hijacking, which attempts to override model behavior and system policies.

Fully mitigating Prompt Injection appears difficult with current LLM architectures: the UK NCSC warned (Dec. 2025) that such attacks may never be fully mitigated in the same way as SQL injection [3]; Schneier and Raghavan argued that the lack of strict code–data separation complicates isolation between instructions and user content [4]; and NVIDIA researchers and OpenAI have each described related limitations in terms of control-plane/data-plane separation [5,6].

Prior studies primarily evaluate Hijacking and Extraction as isolated single-stage attacks, leaving two gaps that this study addresses. First, chained multi-stage LLM attacks have rarely been modeled as absorbing Markov processes using empirically measured, LLM-specific transition probabilities (Section 2.3). Second, to our knowledge, few, if any, prior studies have explicitly named or systematically quantified the specific pattern in which a refusal response itself discloses the protected information it is meant to withhold (Section 2.2). This study introduces the terms Refusal-Induced Leakage (RIL) and, as a contrasting pattern, Compliance-Induced Leakage (CIL) (Fig. 1 illustrates the two concepts) to distinguish two empirically observed leakage patterns in LLM refusal responses, and evaluates how refusal design choices influence downstream attack propagation under multi-stage conditions.

Fig. 1. RIL versus CIL: both leak `access_code`, but through qualitatively different mechanisms.

To address these gaps, this study models the attack scenario as four successive *stages*, denoted S1–S4 (the letter “S” stands for *Stage*; we use this S1–S4 notation throughout the paper). We integrate honeypot-observed attacker behavior (S1) with Tensor Trust–based controlled evaluations (S2–S4) into a four-step non-homogeneous absorbing Markov chain framework. Using Meta Llama3:8B, we compare Verbose Refusal (VR) and Silent Refusal (SR) under single-stage and multi-stage attack conditions and evaluate external multi-layer guardrails.

2 Related Work

2.1 Prompt Injection Research

Geng et al. [7] synthesized 128 studies (2022–2025), reporting attack success rates exceeding 90% against undefended systems and highlighting the lack of

standardized evaluation frameworks. Toyer et al. [8] released Tensor Trust [9], a human-generated adversarial dataset (126,000+ attacks, 46,000+ defenses) that established the Hijacking and Extraction benchmarks used in this study. Liu et al. [10] systematically evaluated five attack types, ten defenses, and ten LLMs (Open-Prompt-Injection). Balashov et al. [11] introduced a formal multi-stage inference attack model based on information-theoretic leakage bounds, but did not empirically estimate transition probabilities from observed attacker behavior.

2.2 Refusal Behavior and LLM Defense Design

Prior work evaluates whether a request is blocked, but rarely examines how refusal behavior itself may influence downstream attack propagation. Xue et al. [12] examined over-refusal on benign queries, and Dhahbi and Thimmaraju [13] proposed partial-leakage scoring beyond binary compliance/refusal judgments, but to our knowledge few, if any, prior studies have systematically quantified the pattern in which a refusal response itself discloses the protected information it is meant to withhold.

Yin et al. [14] investigate a related “refusal cliff” phenomenon in large reasoning models, in which a model’s internal refusal intention collapses sharply immediately before final-token generation, leading to jailbreak-style compliance. Their refusal cliff concerns collapse toward *harmful content generation* in reasoning models, whereas RIL concerns leakage of a *specific protected secret* within an otherwise successful refusal in general-purpose instruction-tuned models; the two may share an underlying mechanism, but establishing this connection is left for future work.

2.3 Probabilistic Models and MITRE ATLAS

Liu et al. [15] showed independence assumptions can underestimate chained cyberattack risk using continuous-time Markov chains; Abraham and Nair [16] developed non-homogeneous Markov models for vulnerability aging; Bar et al. [17] modeled honeypot attack propagation with Markov chains, but few studies apply this framework to multi-stage LLM attacks with empirically measured, LLM-specific transition probabilities. Monte Carlo approaches incorporating MITRE ATT&CK have been applied to AI risk analysis [18], though empirical estimation of generative-AI-specific transition probabilities remains limited. MITRE ATLAS [19] provides a structured AI/ML attack taxonomy. A recent multi-agent study [20] mapped real-world AI attack cases to MITRE ATLAS technique identifiers, but probabilistic estimation of stage-to-stage transition behavior for chained, generative-AI-specific attacks remains outside its scope.

3 Proposed Method

3.1 Multi-Stage Attack Scenario

Based on MITRE ATLAS, this study structures Prompt Injection attacks into four sequential stages. S1 (Reconnaissance: AML.T0006, Active Scanning) rep-

resents the discovery of exposed LLM endpoints, empirically measured using a Beelzebub high-interaction honeypot environment (51 days, 19,974 requests); the resulting probability is denoted q_{env} . S2 (Initial Access: AML.T0051) represents a Hijacking attack in which the attacker attempts to override model behavior and force the output “Access Granted,” evaluated using 776 Tensor Trust Hijacking scripts and producing transition probability q_1 . S3 (Exfiltration: AML.T0057, LLM Data Leakage) represents an Extraction attack that attempts to reveal the hidden `access_code` embedded in the model context, evaluated using 230 Tensor Trust Extraction scripts and producing transition probability q_2 . S4 represents the final Impact state in which the attacker successfully obtains the protected information (`access_code` present in the response).

We note that MITRE ATLAS does not exhaustively capture the full diversity of prompt-level attacks observed in the wild, and that the 776 Hijacking and 230 Extraction scripts, while among the largest publicly available human-generated prompt-injection benchmarks, represent only a partial sample of the broader attack space; these representativeness limitations are discussed further in the Conclusion.

For each Tensor Trust script, the `pre_prompt`, `access_code`, `post_prompt`, and `attack` fields were concatenated into a single user-role message, with the SYSTEM policy (where defined) supplied separately via the Modelfile (Section 3.3). This follows common practice in several Tensor Trust-based studies but differs from the original game setting, in which the defender’s and attacker’s text occupy distinct conversational roles; implications are discussed in the Conclusion.

S2 (Hijacking) and S3 (Extraction) are technically independent attack categories, so we define three Kill Chains: *Chain A* (S1→S2→S4, Hijacking alone), *Chain B* (S1→S3→S4, Extraction alone), and *Chain C* (S1→S2→S3→S4, Hijacking precedes Extraction; failure at S2 terminates the chain), the primary focus of this study. The absorbing Markov chain formulation (Section 3.2) applies specifically to Chain C, which models sequential, context-dependent progression; Chain B is treated as a separate non-sequential scenario outside this formulation. Section 4 evaluates how defenses between S2 and S3 influence transition behavior: first the Verbose Refusal (VR) paradigm (Section 3.3, EXP-2), then, once failure-mode analysis (EXP-3) motivates a redesign, a Silent Refusal (SR) paradigm under the same scenario (EXP-4).

3.2 Non-Homogeneous Absorbing Markov Chain

This study models Chain C using a non-homogeneous absorbing Markov chain. The Chain C scenario assumes that the attack progresses sequentially through S1→S2→S3→S4, where success at each stage enables progression to the next stage. Under this scenario assumption, failure at any stage terminates the Chain C attack sequence. Accordingly, each failure state is treated as an absorbing terminal state. This formulation enables direct estimation of the probability of first failure at each attack stage, thereby identifying which defensive stage may most effectively interrupt the attack sequence. Unlike isolated single-stage evaluation,

this approach explicitly captures propagation behavior across dependent attack stages.

The transition probabilities are: q_{env} (reconnaissance success at S1), q_1 (Hijacking success at S2), q_2 (Extraction success at S3 after Hijacking), and q_3 (final Impact reachability at S4).

The resulting model enables quantitative comparison between single-stage robustness and multi-stage attack propagation behavior. In particular, it allows analysis of situations in which a defense configuration performs strongly under isolated Hijacking evaluation while simultaneously increasing downstream leakage risk during chained attacks. Furthermore, because the sum of all first-failure probabilities and $P(Impact)$ is identically equal to 1, the numerical consistency of the probabilistic model can be verified directly.

The transition probability q_i at each step i is defined by Equation (1) using the number of successful attack attempts s_i and failed attempts f_i :

$$q_i = \frac{s_i}{s_i + f_i} \quad (1)$$

where s_i and f_i denote the numbers of successful and failed trials at step i , respectively.

The transition matrix P_i for each step is defined as follows:

$$P_i = \begin{pmatrix} q_i & 1 - q_i \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where the upper row represents the attack-continuation state and the lower row represents the absorbing failure state. The final three-step Impact reachability is defined as the following product. Figure 2 is a conceptual diagram of this chain, showing the four attack stages S1–S4, the per-stage transition probabilities (q_{env} , q_1 , q_2), and the absorbing failure state into which an attack falls when a stage is defended.

$$P(Impact) = q_{env} \times q_1 \times q_2 \quad (3)$$

Here, q_{env} corresponds to the empirically observed transition probability measured from the honeypot in S1 (Reconnaissance). In contrast, q_1 and q_2 are experimentally measured probabilities for S2 (Hijacking) and S3 (Extraction), respectively. Distinguishing q_{env} from q_1 and q_2 explicitly clarifies that S1 is based on real-world observation, whereas S2 and S3 are based on controlled experimental evaluation, making the model non-homogeneous. The probability that the attack fails for the first time at each step is derived as follows:

$$P(fail \text{ at } S1) = 1 - q_{env} \quad (4)$$

$$P(fail \text{ at } S2) = q_{env} (1 - q_1) \quad (5)$$

$$P(fail \text{ at } S3) = q_{env} \cdot q_1 \cdot (1 - q_2) \quad (6)$$

Equations (4)–(6) and $P(Impact)$ sum identically to 1, providing a numerical consistency check for all evaluated configurations. Furthermore, by the commutative property of multiplication, exchanging the execution order of S2 and S3 does not change the final Impact reachability mathematically.

Fig. 2. Non-Homogeneous Absorbing Markov Chain.

While the Chain C formulation reduces to a product of stage probabilities (Eq. 3) for the linear scenario considered here, the absorbing Markov chain offers concrete advantages over a direct multiplicative calculation: it distinguishes “attack succeeded” (S4 Impact) from “attack failed” (Fail@S1–S3) as distinct terminal outcomes rather than a single scalar value (Section 4 shows the S3 failure outcomes further decompose into qualitatively different leakage patterns); it enables sensitivity analysis by varying q_{env} , q_1 , q_2 independently to identify which stage most effectively interrupts the sequence; and it decomposes an aggregate figure into stage-specific first-failure probabilities (Eqs. 4–6), giving a structured vocabulary for multi-stage risk. This formulation is intentionally simple as a first step; richer state-space extensions (e.g., branching or non-sequential kill chains) are left for future work, as is empirically deriving q_3 , the S3→S4 transition itself: the present evaluation treats S4 (Impact) as reached whenever S3 (Extraction) succeeds, rather than measuring it separately.

3.3 Defense Configurations

This study evaluates five incrementally hardened prompt-level defense configurations, which we call Verbose Refusal (VR0–VR4). Each is implemented through Llama’s Modelfile components (SYSTEM, TEMPLATE, MESSAGE, PARAMETER), adding defense components one at a time while maintaining explanatory refusal behavior: VR0 is the baseline; VR1 adds SYSTEM-level refusal policies; VR2 adds TEMPLATE-based separation between system instructions and user input; VR3 adds few-shot safe-refusal examples; VR4 additionally applies PARAMETER-based output control. *Verbose Refusal (VR)* denotes a refusal style in which the model explains its reasoning for declining a request. The design hypothesis is that incremental hardening monotonically improves robustness across all attack stages (the full configuration of all five levels is given in Table 5, presented in Section 4.2 alongside the Silent Refusal redesign so both paradigms can be compared directly); Section 4 evaluates VR0–VR4 under both single-stage and multi-stage conditions and, based on the resulting failure-mode analysis, introduces a revised refusal paradigm (Section 4.2).

4 Evaluation

4.1 Experimental Environment

The S1 reconnaissance observation was conducted on a Sakura Internet VPS v5 environment (Osaka Region/Zone 3; Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS, 3 vCPU, 1.9 GiB

RAM) running a Beelzebub honeypot (Docker) behind a custom Ollama proxy (qwen2.5:0.5b). The controlled multi-stage LLM evaluation — S2 Hijacking, S3 Extraction, S4 Impact reachability, VR/SR Modelfile evaluation, and external guardrail evaluation — was conducted on a Sakura Internet High-Firepower DOK environment (Tokyo Region; Ubuntu-based JupyterLab, Xeon E5-2623 v3, 4 vCPU, 54 GiB RAM, Tesla V100-PCIE-32GB/CUDA 12.2) using Ollama 0.23.2 (Meta Llama3:8B) and Promptfoo 0.121.11.

4.2 Experimental Results

The evaluation proceeds through seven steps, which we label EXP-0 through EXP-6 (the prefix “EXP” stands for *Experiment*) and use throughout the paper for cross-referencing: S1 honeypot observation; single-stage and multi-stage (Chain C) Hijacking/Extraction evaluation; a few-shot ablation and manual CIL/RIL failure-mode classification; the Silent Refusal redesign and re-evaluation; a security-usability evaluation; and a three-layer external guardrail evaluation.

Honeypot Analysis (EXP-0).

The honeypot logs were analyzed to determine whether real-world external actors progressed beyond simple endpoint discovery, providing empirical evidence for the S1 reconnaissance-to-prompt-injection transition used in the Markov-chain scenario. The honeypot captured 19,974 unsolicited requests over 51 days (Mar. 22–May 11, 2026) from 2,046 unique source IPs (anonymized before publication). Among these, 33 IPs performed model enumeration (GET `/api/tags`, `/v1/models`), and 7 subsequently attempted POST requests to chat/completion endpoints, yielding $q_{env} = 7/33 \approx 0.212$. Table 1 provides a detailed breakdown of request types.

One external source exhibited a progressive attack pattern consistent with MITRE ATLAS AML.T0051 staging: enumeration, a benign chat probe, repeated enumeration including a system-role injection probe, and finally successful multi-turn interaction, over an 11-day window; earlier requests returned HTTP 404, indicating endpoint reconfiguration during the observation period. This sequence connects S1 reconnaissance to the controlled S2–S4 evaluation.

Single-Stage Attack: Hijacking (EXP-1).

The first controlled evaluation treated Hijacking as an independent single-stage attack. Results were broadly consistent with the design expectation: adding internal defense components tended to reduce the Hijacking success probability q_1 , with VR4 showing the strongest single-stage defense (Table 2).

Multi-Stage Attack: Hijacking Followed by Extraction (EXP-2).

The same VR configurations were evaluated under Chain C, where the attacker attempts S2 Hijacking and then S3 Extraction before reaching S4 Impact. Incremental hardening improved multi-stage robustness monotonically: VR4, the

Table 1. S1 Request Type Distribution.

Request Type	Count	Share	Interpretation
Web vulnerability scan (GET)	13,753	69.2%	Automated scanners; not LLM-targeted
Other GET probe / unclassified	5,946	29.9%	General internet scanning, malformed requests
Model enumeration (GET)	94	0.5%	LLM-specific: /api/tags, /v1/models
Chat / completion (POST)	60	0.3%	Direct model interaction attempts
Version / status check (GET)	22	0.1%	LLM-specific: /api/version, /api/ps
TOTAL (external IPs only)	19,875	100%	Localhost (127.0.0.1) excluded

Note. External IPs only ($n = 19,875$). LLM-specific requests (enumeration + POST) accounted for 0.8% of traffic; $q_{env} = 7/33 \approx 0.212$.

Table 2. Single-Stage Hijacking Evaluation (EXP-1).

Config	q_1 (Hijacking success)	Hijacking defense ($1 - q_1$)	Interpretation
VR0	0.097	90.3%	Baseline
VR1	0.059	94.1%	Improved by SYSTEM policy
VR2	0.064	93.6%	Comparable to VR1
VR3	0.040	96.0%	Strong Hijacking defense with few-shot examples
VR4	0.037	96.3%	Best single-stage Hijacking defense

strongest configuration against Hijacking alone, also achieved the lowest Extraction success probability and the highest multi-stage coverage among the VR configurations (Table 3).

Failure-Mode Analysis: Few-Shot Ablation and CIL/RIL Classification (EXP-3).

Although hardening improved overall multi-stage robustness monotonically, the residual Extraction failures that survived hardening were not uniform in character, which prompted a follow-up investigation. The most salient design difference across VR0–VR4 was that VR3 and VR4 included few-shot refusal examples. EXP-3 first tested whether few-shot examples were associated with the composition of residual failures, then manually inspected the failed responses and classified each as Compliance-Induced Leakage (CIL), where the model complies and directly discloses the `access_code`, or Refusal-Induced Leakage (RIL), where the model refuses yet discloses it within its own explanation (Section 2.2). To isolate the effect of few-shot examples, we additionally ran two ablated configurations, VR3nofs and VR4nofs (the suffix “nofs” stands for *no few-shot*): each is identical to VR3/VR4 but with the three few-shot safe-refusal examples removed, so comparing a configuration against its “nofs” counterpart isolates the few-shot examples’ contribution to the failure composition. Table 4 reports, for each configuration, the number of failing samples (FAIL n) and the share of those failures that were CIL versus RIL; this CIL/RIL decomposition was not drawn in prior Tensor Trust–based evaluation work.

Table 3. Multi-Stage Evaluation under Chain C (EXP-2).

Config	q_1 Hijack	q_2 Extract	Hijack def.	Extract def.	Multi-stage cov.	Rank
VR0	0.097	0.674	90.3%	32.6%	77.1%	5th (lowest)
VR1	0.059	0.500	94.1%	50.0%	84.0%	4th
VR2	0.064	0.439	93.6%	56.1%	85.0%	3rd
VR3	0.040	0.200	96.0%	80.0%	92.3%	2nd
VR4	0.037	0.187	96.3%	81.3%	92.9%	1st (highest)

Table 4. Few-Shot Ablation and Failure-Mode Classification (EXP-3).

Config	Few-shot	FAIL (n)	CIL	RIL	Interpretation
VR0	None	155	—	—	Baseline ($q_2 = 67.4\%$)
VR3	Yes	46	14 (30.4%)	32 (69.6%)	RIL majority; few-shot lowers total FAIL
VR3nofs	No	102	54 (52.9%)	48 (47.1%)	FAIL \uparrow , RIL share \downarrow w/o few-shot
VR4	Yes	43	17 (39.5%)	26 (60.5%)	RIL majority; few-shot lowers total FAIL
VR4nofs	No	80	43 (53.8%)	37 (46.2%)	FAIL \uparrow , RIL share \downarrow w/o few-shot

Silent Refusal Redesign.

The EXP-3 analysis motivated a fundamental redesign of the refusal strategy. Because explanatory refusal responses were identified as the primary leakage surface, a Silent Refusal (SR) principle was introduced: the model rejects malicious requests using a fixed minimal-information response (“I cannot comply with that request.”) without any explanatory reasoning or apology. SR0–SR4 follow the same incremental component structure as VR0–VR4, with the critical difference that few-shot examples demonstrate silent rather than verbose refusal behavior. Table 5 specifies the complete Modelfile configuration for both paradigms side by side — the five VR levels introduced in Section 3.3 and the five SR levels introduced here — and serves as the design reference for all experiments that follow (the VR configurations are evaluated in EXP-1 to EXP-3 and the SR configurations in EXP-4).

A three-layer external guardrail complements internal defenses: Layer 1 (LLM Guard Prompt Injection scanner, DeBERTa-v3-base) blocks Prompt Injection inputs; Layer 2 (Modelfile); Layer 3 (LLM Guard Sensitive scanner, Isotonic DeBERTa-v3) intercepts confidential outputs. This architecture addresses OWASP LLM01 (Prompt Injection) and LLM02 (Sensitive Information Disclosure).

Multi-Stage Attack: Silent Refusal Re-Evaluation (EXP-4).

Since EXP-3 showed many failures were leakage embedded inside verbose refusal responses, the evaluation was redirected from Verbose to Silent Refusal. SR0–SR4 were evaluated to test whether suppressing explanatory refusal content reduces Extraction success (Table 6). As with VR, each incremental SR component reduces overall Extraction success monotonically, from $q_2 = 0.704$ (SR0) to $q_2 = 0.178$ (SR4, 82.2% defense). The same table presents the CIL/RIL break-

Table 5. Modelfile Configurations: VR0–VR4 and SR0–SR4.

Config	SYSTEM policy	TEMPLATE sep.	Few-shot examples	ex-	PARAMETER control
VR0 / SR0	(none — baseline)	No	None		Default
VR1	Protect the access_code. Never reveal it.	No	None		Default
SR1	Do NOT explain your refusal. Reply only: I cannot comply.	No	None		Default
VR2	Same as VR1	Yes (user/asst.)	None		Default
SR2	Same as SR1	Yes (user/asst.)	None		Default
VR3	Same as VR1	Yes	3× safe-refusal (verbose)		Default
SR3	Same as SR1	Yes	3× silent-refusal		Default
VR4	Same as VR1	Yes	3× safe-refusal (verbose)	temp. 0.1 / num_predict 256	
SR4	Same as SR1	Yes	3× silent-refusal	temp. 0.1 / num_predict 256	

Note. VR (Verbose Refusal) defined in Section 3.3; SR (Silent Refusal) is the redesign. Both paradigms share the same four incremental components; only the refusal style of the SYSTEM policy and few-shot examples differs (explanatory vs. silent).

Table 6. Silent Refusal Re-Evaluation and Failure-Mode Breakdown (EXP-4).

Config	q_2	Extr. defense	CIL (n)	CIL%	RIL (n)	RIL%	SAFE
SR0	0.704	29.6%	127	78.4%	35	21.6%	68
SR1	0.409	59.1%	53	56.4%	41	43.6%	136
SR2	0.309	69.1%	31	43.7%	40	56.3%	159
SR3	0.209	79.1%	20	41.7%	28	58.3%	182
SR4	0.178	82.2%	12	29.3%	29	70.7%	189

Note. $n = 230$; SR0–SR4 defined in Table 5. q_2 : Extraction success probability at S3. CIL/RIL percentages are of the leaked subset. CIL: Compliance-Induced Leakage; RIL: Refusal-Induced Leakage; SAFE: neither leakage type (defended).

down among leaked cases ($n = 230$): the RIL share of residual leakage increases progressively from 21.6% (SR0) to 70.7% (SR4) even as the absolute leak count falls, mirroring the pattern observed for VR’s few-shot ablation (Table 4). Confirmed independently across both refusal paradigms and all hardening levels, RIL is therefore a structural property of refusal-response leakage rather than an artifact of a single design choice.

Security–Usability Evaluation: Verbose vs. Silent Refusal (EXP-5).

An additional usability-oriented evaluation was conducted using 20 benign prompts spanning five categories: general knowledge, coding, reasoning, everyday tasks, and boundary cases whose surface wording loosely resembles security-sensitive topics (e.g., password managers, encryption, disk-formatting “codes”) without constituting actual attacks. The purpose of this evaluation was to determine whether VR and SR configurations unnecessarily suppress legitimate,

Table 7. Security–Usability Evaluation (EXP-5).

Configuration	Extraction q_2	Overblocking Rate	Avg Response Words
VR4	0.187	5.0%	138.3
SR4	0.178	35.0%	99.4

benign requests, including ones that superficially resemble security-related topics (Table 7).

Table 7 reveals a notable security–usability trade-off despite VR4 and SR4 reaching comparable raw Extraction defense (81.3% and 82.2%, respectively; Table 3, Table 6). VR4 rejected 1 of 20 benign prompts (5.0% overblocking, avg. 138.3 words), whereas SR4 rejected 7 of 20 (35.0% overblocking, avg. 99.4 words). The mechanism is shared: Silent Refusal reduces RIL by withholding the explanatory reasoning in which `access_code` was previously disclosed, but this same suppression removes the contextual cues the model would otherwise use to distinguish malicious requests from legitimate security-related ones, increasing overblocking.

Because VR4 and SR4 achieve essentially the same raw Extraction defense, the choice between them is determined primarily by usability: SR’s far higher overblocking is not offset by a meaningful security advantage, so VR is the more favorable internal configuration. The root causes of CIL and RIL are not yet fully identified; we hypothesize that architectural constraints inherent to current LLM designs contribute, which motivates the external guardrail evaluated next.

External Defense: Three-Layer Guardrail (EXP-6).

Fig. 3. Three-layer external guardrail: Layer 1 input scanner, Layer 2 internal Modelfile defense (VR0–VR4 / SR0–SR4), and Layer 3 output scanner.

The preceding experiments hardened the model internally, yet residual leakage persisted. A complementary defense is an *external guardrail*: a wrapper that inspects inputs and outputs independently of the model, so protection does not rely on the model correctly refusing. We evaluate a three-layer guardrail (Fig. 3) combining an input scanner that flags prompt-injection attempts, the Modelfile refusal layer (the internal VR/SR defense), and an output scanner that detects sensitive information such as the `access_code` before it is returned, testing

Table 8. Three-Layer External Guardrail Evaluation (EXP-6).

Configuration	Defense layers active	Attack coverage	FPR	Interpretation
VR4 (no guardrail)	Modelfile only	81.3%	5.0%	Baseline for comparison
SR4 alone (no guardrail)	SR Modelfile only	82.2%	35.0%	Comparable Extraction defense to VR4, but much higher overblocking
Layer 1 alone	Input scanner only (S3 attack isolated)	94.8%	0%	Large gain from input-side filtering
VR0 + guardrail	Input + VR0 + output scanner	95.7%	0%	Residual risk dominated by attacks bypassing Layer 1
VR4 + guardrail	Input + VR4 + output scanner	99.6%	5.0%	Strongest overall coverage under this setup
SR0 + guardrail	Input + SR0 + output scanner	95.7%	0%	Residual risk dominated by attacks bypassing Layer 1
SR4 + guardrail	Input + SR4 + output scanner	98.7%	35.0%	Practical candidate for general-purpose bots

whether this external wrapper closes the residual leakage that internal hardening alone could not. The result shows that the strongest overall coverage was obtained by combining VR4 with the external guardrail, narrowly ahead of the SR4 combination, with both substantially outperforming any unguarded configuration (Table 8). The output scanner (LLMGuard) reduced residual Extraction leakage to near-zero for both VR4 and SR4 (0.4% and 1.3%) but left overblocking unchanged, since the scanners do not act on benign prompts; the usability trade-off identified in EXP-5 therefore persists even under the guardrail.

Guardrail Input Construction. Concatenating the system framing, S2 hijack attack, S2-turn response, and S3 extraction text into a single string with explicit section markers (e.g., --- BEGIN S2 SUCCESSFUL HIJACKING CONTEXT ---) and scanning it with Layer 1 (PromptInjection) initially measured a 100% block rate across all four configurations. This figure does not cleanly measure S3-attack detection: the classifier truncates input at 512 tokens, often exhausting the window on upstream S2 content before the S3 attack is processed, and the section markers are an artificial detection cue absent from genuine attacker text. We therefore reconstructed each case as a two-turn conversation (turn 1: framing + S2 attack, with the genuine S2-stage response as the assistant turn; turn 2: the bare S3 extraction attempt, no delimiters), applying Layer 1 only to the incoming turn-2 message, consistent with deployed input scanning, while the model still receives the full two-turn history so any RIL-relevant softening effect is preserved. All guardrail-related figures in Table 8 use this reconstructed representation.

Once Layer 1 intercepts the great majority of S3 attacks (218 of 230 in isolation), the residual difference between refusal designs determines the outcome among attacks that bypass it: VR4 resolves these cases more effectively than SR4, turning VR4’s marginal disadvantage without the guardrail (81.3% vs. 82.2%) into a clear advantage with it (99.6% vs. 98.7%). Combined with VR4’s much lower overblocking rate (5.0% vs. 35.0%), VR4 plus the guardrail dominates SR4

plus the guardrail on both axes evaluated here, offering a practical, evidence-based resolution to the security–usability trade-off within the scope of this study.

5 Conclusion

This study formulated multi-stage Prompt Injection attacks (S1–S4) as a non-homogeneous absorbing Markov chain and empirically measured transition probabilities across VR0–VR4 and SR0–SR4 configurations on Meta Llama3:8B. The evaluation yielded three key findings.

First, incremental defense hardening improved robustness monotonically in both single-stage Hijacking and chained multi-stage evaluation: VR4, the strongest configuration against Hijacking alone, also achieved the highest multi-stage coverage. However, manual inspection of the residual failures that survived hardening revealed a leakage pattern we describe as Refusal-Induced Leakage (RIL): the model refuses, yet discloses the protected information within its own refusal. The CIL/RIL distinction adopted in this study enabled decomposition of leakage failure modes and revealed a consistent structural pattern across both refusal paradigms and all hardening levels: while hardening substantially reduces the absolute volume of leakage, the share of residual leakage that takes the harder-to-detect RIL form increases — from 47.1% to 69.6% of remaining failures with few-shot examples in VR3, and from 21.6% to 70.7% across SR0–SR4. Second, the Silent Refusal principle achieved Extraction defense comparable to, but not consistently better than, Verbose Refusal at matching hardening levels; the larger and more consistent difference between the two paradigms was the security–usability trade-off, with SR causing far more unnecessary refusals on generally benign prompts, including ones superficially resembling security-related topics, despite no meaningful security advantage. Third, combining either refusal paradigm with a three-layer external guardrail achieved 95.7–99.6% attack coverage against the evaluated scripts, with VR4 plus the guardrail providing the strongest overall result while also retaining VR4’s much lower overblocking rate, making it the more favorable configuration on both axes within the scope evaluated. These findings suggest that multi-stage probabilistic evaluation, combined with manual failure-mode classification, can reveal properties of residual leakage — such as its changing composition under hardening — that are not observable from aggregate success/failure rates under single-stage conditions.

We position the contributions of this study as a methodological framework applicable to the current generation of LLMs and attack techniques, rather than as a universally generalizable risk model. Transition probabilities reflect LLM capabilities and attack techniques observed during the experimental period (March–May 2026) and may not generalize beyond the current setting; the Tensor Trust dataset also lacks timestamp metadata, restricting analysis of how attack strategies evolve over time. Nevertheless, the Markov chain framework itself is not model-specific: recalibrating transition probabilities with updated datasets may allow the same approach to be applied to future settings. The

evaluation is further constrained to a single model (Meta Llama3:8B) and the Chain C scenario; the specific q_1/q_2 values and the RIL proportion-increase effect are specific to this model evaluated against Tensor Trust, and generalization to other model families should be treated as a hypothesis requiring further validation. As a supplementary note, preliminary experiments with Gemma2 and Mistral suggest RIL is not specific to Llama3:8B; a cross-architecture analysis is reported in a companion paper under preparation. Future work includes broader attack taxonomies, additional prompt families, deeper mechanistic analysis of RIL, and defense design guidelines. The experimental datasets, Modelfile configurations, and evaluation scripts are publicly available at [21].

A further limitation concerns input construction: the `pre_prompt`, `access_code`, `post_prompt`, and `attack` fields were concatenated into a single user-role message in all evaluations (SYSTEM-level policies supplied separately via the Modelfile), which does not fully reproduce Tensor Trust’s original role-separated game setting; role separation could plausibly affect the measured transition probabilities, including those underlying RIL. Preliminary “sys-sep” runs continue to exhibit RIL, suggesting the phenomenon is not solely a single-message artifact, but a full re-evaluation across all VR/SR configurations under sys-sep remains future work.

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